

Assessment of Teacher-Student Relationship on Academic Performance in Christian Religious Knowledge among Secondary School Students in Kaduna State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Relationships are very of great importance to every setting ranging from the family, school and the larger society. It is in this regard that this study assessed teacher-student relationship on academic performance in Christian Religious Knowledge among secondary school students in Kaduna State, Nigeria. Survey design, specifically, descriptive was adopted. The objectives were to examine teacher-student romantic and work relationships on academic performance in Christian Religious knowledge. Two research questions and two hypotheses were formulated in line with objectives. Questionnaires and interviews were adopted and used as instruments for data collection from the seven hundred and four (704) respondents sampled to represent the population of thirteen thousand, nine hundred and sixty-four secondary school Christian students (13,864), and nine thousand, four hundred and five teachers (9,403). A pilot study was conducted to validate the instrument. The data were analyzed using Cronbach's Alfa method at a 0.05 level of tolerance. The reliability coefficient obtained was 0.873 and the standard Alfa level of .873. These were considered adequate for the internal consistency of the instrument with a confirmation of its reliability. The data was subjected to statistical analysis using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), IBM version 26. Statistical procedures adopted were descriptive statistics such as frequencies and percentages, mean, and standard deviation. Findings revealed that teachers who engage in romantic relationship with students favour those students, even if they are not qualified. Another finding revealed that teacher-student work relationship fosters a welcoming classroom atmosphere where students feel secure, valued, and confident to perform better in class. As a result, the study concluded that teacher-student relationship has a high tendency of reducing Christian student academic performance, while teacher-student work relationship help student to record high academic performance. The study recommended that Kaduna state Teacher's Service Board in collaboration with Adolescent Girl Initiative Learning Empowerment (AGILE), and the ministry of education should give incentives to teachers who maintain work relationship with their student through recommendations by school managements. They should also establish and enforce clear policies regarding teacher-student relationship and give sanctions to anyone found guilty of the act.

Keywords: Teacher, Relationship, Academic performance, Christian students.

Introduction

Generally, relationships are very important in every setting ranging from the family, school, and the larger society; and its values can never be over-emphasized. Studies have shown that for children to learn, they need a relationship by attaching themselves to adults i.e. their parents, older siblings, and teachers. Mikulince and Shaver (2020) maintain that for normal development, children need to attach themselves to an adult if not, they will lack the ability to meet their own survival requirements and endanger their lives. Teenagers in secondary school, spend a considerable amount of time at School from approximately 175 to 220 days with an average of 5 to 8 hours every day ranging from normal school activities to extra lessons and games. In line with the above assertion, Arrascue (2023) added that children spend 18 years of their lives receiving education beginning at the age of 5. She continued that the formation of a teacher-student relationship is the best practice for bettering education for all students throughout the course of their entire academic career. During these hours and years, students' interactions and subsequent relationships with teachers are paramount for their emotional regulation, attention, problem-solving, and academic achievement (Pianta & Allen, 2018). Cook, Coco, Zhang, Duong, Renshaw, Long, and Frank

(2018) confirmed the above assertion to be true, saying that it is not a surprise if the bond between the students and their teachers impacts their performance positively or negatively depending on which type of relationship exists between them. Teachers have an enormous amount of influence on their students and this influential power has significant implications on the performance of the students. The most powerful weapon teachers have when trying to foster a favorable learning climate, is a positive relationship with their students (Boynton, 2015).

Teaching and learning are as old as man himself and it is considered a noble profession worldwide. Teacher's Registration Council of Nigeria (2013) maintains that "it is the oldest and noblest of all professions." (p. 10). In most of the world's traditional cultures, during teaching and learning, the teacher sits on a stool or a place higher than the learners, while the learners sit on either mat or on the bare floor to show respect and honor, so that all of them will be able to see and hear the teacher. This can be seen in the Islamic and Jewish traditional schools. During the early stage of formal education, learners were highly disciplined and respectful and those who were shouldered with the teaching responsibilities kept their boundaries. Students were obedient, hard-working, and ready to study with all levels of seriousness, humility, and respect. In those days, teachers were highly respected by students, parents, and the entire community in such a way that their opinions were accepted and regarded with utmost dignity; students relate with their teachers with respect even more than they do to their parents. Teachers, on the other hand, were dedicated and determined to carry out their jobs without anyone supervising them as they believed that their reward was in heaven. Rumnanayan and Rao (2014) added that teachers of that time felt it was a good idea to train students to be as excellent as, if not better than them. Similarly, teachers worked hard and left no stone unturned as regards teaching all their topics before the start of the examination and they would not hesitate to take disciplinary actions if required. They maintained that the teacher-student relationship was cordial and that of parent-children. The researcher observes that in the 70s and 80s, students wrote GCE/SSCE with strict supervision, even with policemen in the examination halls, and still excelled without anyone giving them a helping hand or cheating.

When one compares education from its early days through its developmental stages to what is available today, it is obvious that there has been an alteration in the system generally. The opposite appears to be true in today's attitude of teacher-student relationship especially in secondary schools and particularly in the area of morals. Many teachers and students have failed and are found wanting. The respect, honor, and dignity accorded to teachers and the teaching profession by students in those days has completely vanished. The researcher observes that some of the teachers themselves do not know their worth, they go as low as having romantic relationships with their students, especially the male teachers to the female students; while some of them relate with the students as though they are colleagues or age mates. Teachers and students engage in some social activities such as going to parties and clubs; smoking cigarettes and other drugs together, sleeping in the same room, sharing clothes, sending boy students to deliver messages to female students, engaging in examination malpractice, and so on. This is not completely exceptional for female teachers.

Tyoakaa (2014) explained that student misbehavior is high and failure, particularly in external examinations such as WASCE, NECO, JAMB, and others, is poor. He added that this may be attributed to the fact that students do not have a positive and morally guided relationship with their teachers, that is why they do not take their studies seriously, bearing in mind that to some extent, teachers may give them a helping hand during examinations. In connection to the above, Adetola (2024) gave a brief analysis and opinion that the most recent results in 2024 showed a decline, with only 72.12% of candidates achieving five credits, including English and mathematics. This 7.69% drop from the previous year is concerning, especially given the large number of candidates—1,805,216—who sat for the exam. The decline may point to systemic issues that need to be addressed, such as overcrowded classrooms, insufficient teaching resources, or broader socio-economic challenges, student's lack of seriousness etc. The WAEC results from 2020 to 2024 demonstrate both progress and setbacks in Nigeria's education sector. The significant improvement in 2021, followed by declines in 2022 and 2024, highlights the need for continuous monitoring and targeted interventions to ensure sustained progress from all the stake holders.

Objective of the study

The study has the following objectives:

1. To investigate teacher-student romantic relationship and its implications on the academic performance of secondary school Christian students in Kaduna state, Nigeria.
2. To examine teacher-student work relationship and its implications on the academic performance of secondary school Christian students in Kaduna state, Nigeria.

Research Question

1. What is teacher-student romantic relationship and its implications on the academic performance of secondary school Christian students in Kaduna state?
2. What is teacher-student work relationship and its implications on the academic performance of secondary school Christian students in Kaduna state?

Research Hypothesis

1. There is no significant difference between the opinions of male and female teachers on teacher-student romantic relationship and its implications on the academic performance of secondary school Christian students in Kaduna state.
2. There is no significant difference between the opinions of teachers teaching in the urban area and those teaching in the rural area on teacher-student work relationship and its implications on the academic performance of secondary school Christian students in Kaduna state.

Methodology

The study used descriptive survey research design, the target population were secondary Christian students and teachers in Kaduna state. A purposive sample of 720 respondents out of 13,864 students and 9,405 was used. Questionnaire and interview were used as instrument for data collection within 8 LGAs in the 3 senatorial zones of the state. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26 was use to analyzed the data based on the 685 questionnaires that returned representing 97.3% and the mean score for the items were based on four-point Likert scale with the midpoint average for decision of item was fixed at 2.50. this implies that, a mean score of 2.50 and above becomes a yardstick for agreement while mean score below 2.50 implies disagreement. The hypothesis was tested with t-test at 0.05 levels of significance.

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents by Teacher Gender

S/N	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
1	Male Teachers	74	61.2
2	Female Teachers	47	38.8
	Total	121	100

Table 1 shows that 74 respondents were male teachers with (61.2%), and 47 respondents with (38.8%) were female teachers. The data implies that male teachers were more than female teachers in responding to the questionnaire on the implications of the relationship.

Table 2: Distribution of Respondents by Student Gender

S/N	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
1	Male Students	321	56.9
2	Female Students	243	43.1
	Total	564	100

Table 2 shows that 321 respondents (56.9%) were male students, while 243 respondents (43.1%) were female students. The data illustrates that there were more male student respondents than female student respondents.

Table 3: Distribution of Respondents by Teacher Location

S/N	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
1	Urban Teachers	69	57
2	Rural Teachers	52	43
	Total	121	100

Table 3 presents the distribution of teachers in urban and rural areas within a sample size of 121 teachers. While 69 teachers working in urban areas represent 57%, 52 teachers who are working in rural areas represent 43% of the total sample. From the above, it shows that the majority of the teachers (57%) are living in urban areas, while 43% of the teachers are in rural areas.

Table 4: Distribution of Respondents by School Type

S/N	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
1	Boarding Students	212	37.6

2	Day Students	352		62.4
	Total	564		100

Table 4 shows that 212 were boarding students, which gave 37.6%, while 352 were Day

Presentation of Results

The results of the data from the returned questionnaire are presented below, following the analysis of the responses of the respondents.

Research Question 1: what is the teacher-student romantic relationship and its implications on the academic performance of secondary school Christian students in Kaduna state?

Table 5: Opinions of respondents on teacher-student romantic relationship and its implications on the academic performance of secondary school Christian students.

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std.
1	Teachers use their position to maltreat learners who refuse to engage in sex with them.	302	211	98	74	3.08	1.01
2	Teachers threaten students with failure if they refuse romantic relationships with them.	266	325	84	10	3.24	0.72
3	It poses fear to especially female students who do not want to engage themselves in romance.	382	276	25	2	3.52	0.58
4	Romantic relationship incapacitates the teacher from correcting and guiding students.	189	391	69	36	3.07	0.76
5	It increases the rate of drop-out when pregnancy occur because of shame.	288	297	81	19	3.25	0.77
Cumulative						3.28	0.79

Decision mean = 2.50

Results in the above table show the mean response of 3.08, 3.24, 3.52, 3.07 and 3.25 with a cumulative mean of 3.28 and a standard deviation of 0.79. This implies that, teacher-student romantic relationship has implications on the academic performance of secondary school Christian students in Kaduna state, Nigeria.

Table 6: Opinions of Respondents on teacher-student work relationships and its implications on the academic performance of secondary school Christian students.

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std.
1	Boundaries are set and maintained between teachers and students.	358	217	67	43	3.30	0.88
2	Students don't go to the teacher's apartment uninvited, especially at night.	603	41	39	2	3.82	0.53
3	Syllabuses are always covered.	397	178	52	58	3.33	0.94
4	It reduces behavioral problems in students.	299	286	73	27	3.29	0.80
5	Students respect teachers by obeying their instructions and teachers reciprocate same.	382	203	25	75	3.30	0.97
Cumulative						3.39	0.84

Decision mean = 2.50

Results in the above table show the mean response of 3.30, 3.82, 3.33, 3.29 and 3.30 with a cumulative mean of 3.39 and a standard deviation of 0.84. This implies that, teacher-student work relationship has implications on the academic performance of secondary school Christian students in Kaduna state, Nigeria.

Research Hypothesis

Table 7: Independent Sample t-test on Opinions of male and female teachers on teacher-student romantic relationship and its implications on secondary school Christian students' academic performance in Kaduna state, Nigeria.

S/N	Variables	N	Mean	Std. Dev	Std. Error	Df	t-cal	t-crit	P
1	Male Teachers	74	3.2144	0.90074	0.03644	119	1.31	1.96	0.66
2	Female Teachers	47	3.1555	0.76419	0.03092				

Calculated $p > 0.05$, calculated $t < 1.96$, at df 119

Table 7 shows that there is no significant difference between the opinions of male and female teachers regarding teacher-student romantic relationships and their implications for the academic performance of secondary school Christian students in Kaduna State. The p-value of 0.66 is higher than the 0.05 alpha level of significance, and the t-calculated value of 1.31 is lower than the critical value of 1.96 at $df = 119$. Consequently, the null hypothesis is retained.

Table 8: Independent Sample t-test on the opinions of teachers teaching in the urban area and those teaching in the rural area on teacher-student work relationship and its implications on the academic performance of secondary school Christian students.

S/N	Variables	N	Mean	Std. Dev	Std. Error	Df	t-cal	t-crit	P
1	Urban Teachers	69	3.4659	0.75792	0.03054	119	1.73	1.96	0.51
2	Rural Teachers	52	3.3815	0.89565	0.03609				

Calculated $p > 0.05$, calculated $t < 1.96$, at df 119

Table 8 reveals that there is no significant difference between the opinions of teachers working in urban and rural areas regarding teacher-student work relationships and their implications for the academic performance of secondary school Christian students in Kaduna State. This conclusion is based on the p-value of 0.51, which is greater than the 0.05 alpha level of significance, and the t-calculated value of 1.73, which is below the critical value of 1.96 at $df = 119$. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted and retained.

Summary of Findings

Based on the data collected and analyzed from the research questions and hypotheses, the study found that teacher-student relationships have significant implications on the academic performance of secondary school Christian students in Kaduna State, Nigeria. The key findings of the study are as follows:

1. Teachers who engage in sexual relationships with students favour such students, even if they are less qualified compared to those who do not participate in such relationships.
2. Students feel comfortable, valued, and confident that their needs are being addressed.

Discussions of Findings

The findings of the study reveal that teachers who engage in sexual relationships with students may favor those students, even if they are less qualified compared to others who do not agree to engage in such relationships. This finding aligns with Okpo's assertion (2022) that teachers have a responsibility to create a fair and equitable learning environment where evaluations are based solely on academic merit and potential. When personal relationships influence academic evaluations, it compromises the integrity of the educational process and can create a hostile environment for students who do not engage in or benefit from such relationships. The findings highlight a breach of professional boundaries and ethical standards within the teaching profession, as educators are expected to maintain professionalism and uphold ethical guidelines that ensure all students are treated equally and fairly as maintained by the Teacher's Registration Council of Nigeria (2013) on sexual misconduct that, "Teachers should not use their position to humiliate, threaten, intimidate, harass or blackmail any learner to submit to selfish motives or to engage in sexual misconduct." This also aligns with the opinions of interviewees 1, 2, 4, 5, 8, and 11, who highlighted the detrimental effects of biased evaluations on the overall educational experience. sometimes lead homosexual, drug, and cultic teachers to influence students into their practices. This observation aligns with the views of Osguthorpe and Sanger as referenced in Lavy and Bocker (2017), who emphasize that teachers must uphold professional standards focused on the educational and developmental needs of students without introducing personal or sexual agendas.

Findings from the study show a good teacher-student relationship fosters a welcoming classroom atmosphere where students feel secure, valued, and confident that their needs are being addressed. This aligns with Aggarwal and Srivastav's (2016) assertion that a positive teacher-student relationship is built on mutual trust and respect. When boundaries are clearly defined and adhered to, students are more likely to feel secure and supported, which fosters a comfortable and effective learning environment. The interviews conducted reveal that students get the necessary support they need to succeed due to the boundaries set between them and their teachers. Upholding these boundaries is crucial for preventing misunderstandings and avoiding situations that might be perceived as favoritism or inappropriate behavior. By restricting unannounced visits to teachers' homes, schools help to ensure a professional environment that protects both students and teachers from potentially compromising situations, thereby fostering a safe and respectful educational setting (Interviewee, 4, 5, 6, 10, 12, 14, and 16). This observation is consistent with the views expressed by Aggarwal and Srivastav (2016), who emphasize that a strong teacher-student relationship is grounded in mutual trust and respect. Adhering to professional boundaries supports this trust, ensuring that all interactions between teachers and students remain within a respectful and ethical framework.

Recommendations

Based on the study's results and conclusions, the following recommendations have been proposed:

1. Government and educational institutions should establish and enforce clear policies regarding teacher-student relationships, explicitly prohibiting any form of sexual relationship between teachers and students by giving sanctions to anyone found guilty of the act.
2. To address these issues effectively, it is crucial to implement comprehensive training and awareness programs for educators on diversity, inclusivity, and respect. Teachers need to be equipped with the knowledge and skills to foster safe and supportive learning environments that honor students' personal boundaries and identities, regardless of sexual orientation or gender identity.

Conclusion

Based on the results of this study, it can be concluded that:

1. Teachers show preferential treatment to students they are sexually involved in sex with, even if those students are less qualified than others who reject their advances.
2. A good teacher-student relationship fosters a welcoming classroom atmosphere where students feel secure, valued, and confident that their needs are being addressed.

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